

5 New Combinations in *Aeonium*, *Cleistocactus* and *Sedum*

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Abstract—Five new combinations in *Aeonium*, *Cleistocactus* and *Sedum* are proposed.

Aeonium igneum (O.Arango) M.H.J.van der Meer **comb. nov.** \equiv *Greenovia ignea* O.Arango (in [Bot. Macaronés. 32: 147. 2023](#)).

Aeonium \times *pedrosalioi* (O.Arango) M.H.J.van der Meer **comb. nov.** \equiv \times *Greenonium pedrosalioi* O.Arango (in [Bot. Macaronés. 33: 40. 2023](#)). Parentage: *Aeonium igneum* (O.Arango) M.H.J.van der Meer \times *Aeonium spathulatum* (Hornem.) Praeger (as *Greenovia ignea* O.Arango \times *Aeonium spathulatum* (Hornem.) Praeger).

Aeonium \times *lajense* (O.Arango) M.H.J.van der Meer **comb. nov.** \equiv \times *Greenonium lajense* O.Arango (in [Collect. Bot. \(Barcelona\) 42\(e008\): 12. 2023](#)). Parentage: *Aeonium aureum* (C.Sm. ex Hornem.) T.H.M.Mes \times *Aeonium saundersii* Bolle (as *Greenovia diplocycla* Webb ex Bolle \times *Aeonium saundersii* Bolle).

Cleistocactus herrerae (L.E.Alomía) M.H.J.van der Meer **comb. nov.** \equiv *Samaipaticereus herrerae* L.E.Alomía (in [Cact.-Advent. Int. \[Almeria\] 36: 149. 2024](#)).

Sedum leiocarpum (H.Sharsm.) M.H.J.van der Meer **comb. nov.** \equiv *Sedella leiocarpa* H.Sharsm. (in [Madroño 5: 192. 1940](#)).

